

Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt
National Metrology Institute

Digital Validation Services For Metrological Software and Data

Welcome to TraCIM

Digitalisation is affecting all domains of economy, industry, and society today. We can observe a steadily increasing number of software and data being utilised to establish more automated and more efficient processes. It is lifting significant potential to create value. At the same time more and more questions are raised on how to ensure trust in decisions and risk management based on outcomes of new digital tools.

In the domain of measurement technology – we call it metrology – the TraCIM (traceability of computationally-intensive metrology) system provides easy-to-use services to validate correct outcomes of calculations and data. It implements a fully automated end-to-end workflow for performing tests. Furthermore, there are interfaces for humans and machines to use the service. In this sense, TraCIM not only creates a modern anchor of trust for digital measurement applications but is also ready to keep up with the high speed of digital innovation.

Services that are operated under the TraCIM trademark fulfil common quality rules for long-term available, easy-to-maintain, and web-based validation. These rules are defined and provided under the auspice of the TraCIM e.V., an association of digital validation experts and national metrology organisations. It was established by European metrology institutes in 2014 and is now celebrating its tenth anniversary.

TraCIM is evolving with the digital transformation. In 2024, PTB launched a substantially improved version of the validation service platform. Further developments have been started, covering the validation of data and very promising implementations of TraCIM tests for the validation of AI-based software in medicine and manufacturing.

Dr. Daniel Hutzschenreuter, Chair of TraCIM e.V., April 2024

TraCIM services of PTB

	Gauss Testing of gaussian minimization algorithms for the following basic geometric elements: 3D Line, Plane, 3D Circle, Cylinder, Cone, and Sphere.
	Chebyshev Testing of Chebyshev minimization algorithms (Minimum-zone method) for the following basic geometric elements: 2D Line, 2D Circle, Plane, Sphere, and Cylinder.
	3D Thread Evaluation Testing of an algorithm for 3D thread evaluation.
	Three-Rosette Method Testing of an algorithm for a reduced error separating method for pitch calibrations.

Services under development

	D-SI data Classification Testing of the machine-usability of XML data such as in digital calibration certificates including measurement data in the D-SI metadata model.
	AI Segmentation of Heart MRI Testing of accuracy of segmentation of heart ventricles within MRI image data in medicine.
	AI-based artefact reduction for industrial CT Testing of AI-based algorithms for artefact reduction in compressed industrial computer tomography images.

Find out more

You would like to find out more about the TraCIM services?
Then visit PTB's TraCIM webpage.

Here you can find a more detailed description of the general test procedure. Each test service comes with a public user manual. Registered users can perform free example tests. Registration is without fee.

PTB's TraCIM Service

The web portal of our TraCIM services.

Our contact e-mail is info.tracim@ptb.de

Quality Rules of the TraCIM e.V.

Publication of the latest version of quality rules.

The contact e-mail of TraCIM e.V. is info@tracim.eu.

The Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, the National Metrology Institute of Germany, is a scientific and technical higher federal authority falling within the competence, of the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action.

Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt
Bundesallee 100
38116 Braunschweig
Germany

www.ptb.de

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